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“ENUMERATE THE AWARENESS AND CHALLENGES OF FINTECH SERVICES AMONG DIFFERENT DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS IN BENGALURU CITY”- AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Financial technology (FinTech) quick development has changed the way financial services are provided, leading to a stronger focus on customer satisfaction in this sector. This study looks at various demographic groups' knowledge of and challenges in using Fintech services in Bengaluru City one of India's major technological hubs. The study looks into how people's awareness, acceptability and use of financial technology services like peer-to-peer lending platforms, digital payments, mobile banking and robo-advisory services are influenced by their age, gender, income, education, and Occupation.

The study accesses the analysis of awareness and Challenges of Fintech Services among the People of Bengaluru City. The primary data are collected by using structured questionnaire from the sample of 100 respondents. The data is collected on the basis of Qualification and the study is focused in the Bengaluru city. Convenient Non-Probability sampling distribution is used for collection of Data.

The results show different levels of adoption and awareness according to demographic traits. While older and lower-income populations show little awareness and have greater difficulties embracing Fintech services, younger, tech-savvy consumers with greater incomes and educational backgrounds show a better level of involvement with these services. Financial literacy, trust issues, and infrastructure availability are among the main Challenges to be considered.

The purpose of this study is to offer useful information to financial institutions, legislators and Fintech companies so they may improve service accessibility, reduce demographic gaps and encourage broader use of Fintech technologies.

Keywords: Fintech awareness, Mobile banking, demographics and technological adoption, financial technology Challenges. Analytics, Automation.

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INTRODUCTION

Innovation is everywhere. When we compare the day and age we live in with 40, 30, or even 20 years ago, we cannot fail to recognize significant changes in all of the fields. Technology has really changed the world to unimaginable extents very rapidly and it seems that the changes never stop. Apart from seeing considerable improvements in the spheres of computer technology, production and telecommunications, the new technologically advanced age changed the world of finance as well.

FINTECH

Fintech a combination of the terms “**financial**” and “**technology**” refers to businesses that use technology to enhance or automate financial services and processes. The term encompasses a rapidly growing industry that serves the interests of both consumers and businesses in multiple ways. From mobile banking and insurance to crypto currency and investment apps, fintech has a seemingly endless array of applications. Fintech includes mobile payments, digital currencies like Bitcoin, alternative lending solutions, crowd funding platforms for small businesses and robo-advisers that allow users to access professional financial advice at little or no cost.

Fintech in India

India’s fintech revolution heralded a new age of banking for the country’s more than 63 million businesses and 190 million unbanked adults who had been on the fringes of financial services for most if not all of their lifetimes. Over the past ten years, the Fintech sector in India has experienced phenomenal growth as it gained momentum following the country’s expansion of internet services. India has the highest FinTech adoption rate globally and is amongst the fastest-growing Fintech markets in the world. Read here to know more about the Fintech sector in India. India is one of the markets for fintech that is expanding the fastest with an adoption rate of 87% compared to the global average of 64%. Currently, there are 2,000 plus DPIIT- recognized Financial Technology (FinTech) start-ups in India with this number is growing fast. India still has 190 million people without access to banking services, making it the country with the second-largest population without such access despite experiencing

tremendous growth in recent years supported by the growing internet adoption. The real story of Fintech in India started in 2016 when the demonetization of the Rs.500 & Rs.1000 currency notes happened. Although few fintech players already existed in the country before 2016 the country was a cash dominant economy.

The Indian Fintech industry ecosystem sees a wide range of sub segments, including Payments, Lending, Wealth Technology (WealthTech), Personal Finance Management, Insurance Technology (Insurtech), Regulation Technology (RegTech), etc. Enabled by UPI, Indian fintech has made rapid gains in the payments space over the past few years. Fintech are expected to play a vital role in increasing financial inclusion and digital adoption. India has 23 Fintech that have gained ‘Unicorn Status’.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Babu, P. V., Agrawal, G., Mohideen, A. S., & Anand, B. (2024).

Users' Perceived Risks and Challenges of FinTech Adoption in India: An Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 4(1).

The purpose of this assessment is to find out how users view the risks connected to FinTech services, with an emphasis on perceived complexity, regulatory uncertainty, lack of knowledge and security and privacy issues. The research findings indicate that users in India face significant perceived risks related to security and privacy, lack of awareness, regulatory uncertainties, and the complexity of FinTech services. These factors collectively hinder the adoption of FinTech, emphasizing the need for improved user education and robust regulatory frameworks to build trust and facilitate wider acceptance.

2. Aldarmi, A. A. (2024).

Fintech Service Quality of Saudi Banks: Digital Transformation and Awareness in Satisfaction, Re-Use Intentions, and the Sustainable Performance of Firms. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2261.

The study aims to investigate the relationship between customer satisfaction and the quality of fintech services, as well as how customer satisfaction affects the inclination to utilize fintech services again. The study also looks into how these linkages are mediated and moderated in the context of Saudi banks' sustainable performance by digital transformation and digital awareness.

3. **Sampat, B., Mogaji, E., & Nguyen, N. P. (2024).**
The dark side of FinTech in financial services: a qualitative enquiry into FinTech developers' perspective.
International Journal of Bank Marketing, 42(1), 38-65.

The study focuses on the role of Fintech Developers on the Dark side of Fintech Services. The thematic analysis identified three themes: regulatory irresponsibility, technical incapacity, and customer vulnerability. Customers are put at risk due to the nation's slow embrace of FinTech, weak current technology infrastructure, data management issues, and restricted data access. Ethical problems arise when privacy regulation is absent. The development of FinTech in Nigeria is further hampered by the brain drain of talented developers and the shortage of skilled developers.

4. **Chettiar, V. M., & Al Hashami, I. M. H.**
An evaluation of fintech services offered by banking sector in sultanate of Oman.

The study's goals were to identify and analyse the fintech services that the top five banks in Oman that are listed on the Muscat Stock Exchange offer, gauge consumer awareness and preferences for these services, and gauge customer satisfaction with these banks' fintech offerings.

5. **Sharmin, S., Prabha, M., Johora, F. T., Mohammad, N., & Hossain, M. A. (2024).**
Open Banking and Information Service: A Strategic Relationship in the FinTech World.
Open Journal of Business and Management, 12(5), 3743-3758.

The study's conclusions show that open banking gives challenger banks a lot of chances to meet unmet consumer needs and

develop cutting-edge financial services that are ingrained in their clients' daily lives. Furthermore, the opportunity evaluation model that has been established has the potential to assist banks in evaluating and choosing workable business ideas for execution. The study's goals are to increase knowledge of open banking's potential, difficulties, and evaluation while highlighting the connection between open banking and information services and creating a model for challenger banks to use when evaluating opportunities.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The financial sector has witnessed a significant advancement in technology which has revolutionized the way clients interact with financial services. The traditional financial services sector has seen a significant transformation due to the swift progress of financial technology or Fintech. Innovative services like digital payments, robo-advisors, mobile banking and block chain-based solutions are made possible by technological advancements and are revolutionizing how consumers engage with financial institutions. But even if these technologies have the ability to improve user experience. Even there is an up gradation in the technology there are few concerns about the security aspects in the fintech services and usage.

In order to provide solution for the following question research is conducted.

- a) How are the people aware about the Fintech services and about also the user safety?
- b) What are the challenges faced by the Fintech User?

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to investigate how customer experience in Bengaluru one of the IT hubs of India is being impacted by Fintech technological breakthroughs. It will concentrate on the metropolitan populace that actively uses digital banking services. The research will look at number of new Fintech technologies including payment gateways and mobile banking apps like UPI, AI-powered financial products like such as chatbots and robo-advisors. It includes the study about the

awareness about the Fintech Services and also about the challenges faced by the user in the Bengaluru City.

LIMITATION

The study is limited to Bengaluru City which may not concentrate on the other cities in the India. The survey might not fully represent customers who are unfamiliar with or have restricted access to Fintech services. The study may mainly rely on data that is readily available to the public questionnaires or interviews which might not give a clear picture of how modern technologies affect the customer experience.

OBJECTIVES

- To understand the overview of Fintech services.
- To understand the level of awareness about Fintech services among consumers in Bengaluru City.
- To understand the Challenges Faced in Fintech Services adoption.

Sampling Design

In the study 100 respondents have been taken in order to evaluate the awareness and Challenges of the fintech services. The awareness about the fintech services have been taken on the basis of Qualification of the users in the Bengaluru city. Qualification includes High School or Equivalent, PUC, Bachelor’s Degree and Master’s Degree and Other. The data collected through Convenience sampling.

Data Collection Method

- **Survey Method:** A structured questionnaire has framed.
- **Mode of Collection:** Online surveys through platforms like Google Forms, in-person surveys in different areas of Bengaluru.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

➤ **Awareness about Fintech services among consumers in Bengaluru City.**

In order to analysis the awareness about the Fintech Services by users the study is been undertaken in the manner that the users are aware or not aware about the Fintech

services.

Table 1: Evaluation of Awareness level of FinTech Services

Awareness about Fintech	Number of Respondents
Aware	87
Not Aware	13
Total	100

Chart 1: Awareness level of fintech Services.

In the chart No 1, we can draw inference that among the 100 respondents in the Bengaluru city, the awareness of the users of the fintech services, About 87 Respondents (43%) have awareness towards Fintech Services and 13 respondents (7%) have awareness about Fintech Services. The Data is collected from the all the sections of demographic aspects.

1. Awareness level based on the Gender

In order to analysis the Awareness level of the Fintech Services by users based on their Gender Socio Economic Characteristics the Chi Square statistical tool has been adopted. Which helps in the finding the relationship between the Gender and awareness level about Fintech services.

HYPOTHESIS

- **Ho:** There is no relationship between Gender and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.
- **H1:** There is a relationship between Gender and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.

Table 1: Evaluation of Awareness Level Based on Gender

Gender	Awareness about the Fintech Services	Not Awareness about the Fintech Services	Total
Male	34	6	40
Female	53	7	60
Total	87	13	100

The significance level: 0.05, Degree of Freedom: 1 Calculated value is 0.23578 and the table value is 3.841. **Chart No 1:**

Awareness Level Based on Gender

In the Chart No 1. The awareness level of fintech services by the users has been evaluated based on the age socio Economic Characteristics. Calculated value is less than table value so accept the NULL Hypothesis and reject Alternative Hypothesis. So there is a no significance relationship between Gender Demographic factor and Awareness about the Fintech services.

2. Awareness level based on the age

In order to analysis the Awareness level of the Fintech Services by users based on their Age socio Economic Characteristics the Chi Square statistical tool has been adopted. Which helps in the finding the relationship between the age and awareness level about Fintech services.

HYPOTHESIS

- **Ho:** There is no relationship between age factor and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.
- **H1:** There is a relationship between age factor and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.

Table 2: Evaluation of Awareness Level Based on age

Age	Awareness about the Fintech Services	Not Awareness about the Fintech Services	Total
18-24	50	7	57
25-34	33	3	36
35-44	4	1	5
45-54	0	2	2
55-64	0	0	0
65 and above	0	0	0
Total	87	13	100

The significance level: 0.05, Degree of Freedom: 5 Calculated value is 14.32051 and the table value is 11.07 **Chart No 2:**

Awareness Level

Based on Age

In the Chart No 2. The awareness level of fintech services by the users has been evaluated based on the Age Socio Economic Characteristics. Calculated value is more than table value so reject the Null Hypothesis and accept Alternative Hypothesis. So, there is a significance relationship between Age Demographic factor and Awareness about the Fintech services.

3. Awareness level based on Occupation

In order to analysis the Awareness level of the Fintech Services by users based on their Occupation Socio Economic Characteristics the Chi Square statistical tool has been adopted. Which helps in the finding the relationship between the Occupation and awareness level about Fintech services.

Hypothesis

- **Ho:** There is no relationship between **Occupation** factor and the

Awareness about the Fintech Services.

- **H1:** There is a relationship between **Occupation** and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.

Table 3: Evaluation of Awareness Level Based on Occupation

Occupation	Awareness about the Fintech Services	Not Awareness about the Fintech Services	Total
Student	32	06	38
Employed	46	04	50
Self-Employed	01	02	03
Retired	00	00	00
Other	08	01	09
Total	87	13	100

The significance level=0.05, Degree of Freedom: 4 Calculated value is **9.034597** and the table value is **9.488**

Chart No 3: Awareness Level Based on Occupation

In the Chart No 3. The awareness level of fintech services by the users has been evaluated based on the Occupation socio Economic Characteristics. Calculated value is less than table value so accept the NULL Hypothesis and reject Alternative Hypothesis. So there is a no significance relationship between Occupation Demographic factor and Awareness about the Fintech services.

4. Awareness Level Based on Qualification

In order to analysis the Awareness level of the Fintech Services by users based on their Qualification socio Economic Characteristics the chi Square statistical tool

has been adopted. Which helps in the finding the relationship between the Qualification and awareness level.

HYPOTHESIS

- **Ho:** There is no relationship between Qualification demographic factor and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.
- **H1:** There is a relationship between Qualification demographic factor and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.

Table 4: Evaluation of Awareness Level Based on Qualification

Qualification	Awareness about the Fintech Services	Not Awareness about the Fintech Services	Total
High School or Equivalent	02	18	20
PUC	03	17	20
Bachelor's Degree	10	10	20
Master's Degree	15	05	20
Other	18	02	20
Total	87	13	100

The significance level=0.05, Degree of Freedom: 4 Calculated value is **223.4306** and the table value is **9.488**

Chart No 4: Awareness Level Based on Qualification

In the Chart No 4. The awareness level of fintech services by the users has been evaluated based on the Qualification socio Economic Characteristics. Calculated value is more than

table value so reject the NULL Hypothesis and accept Alternative Hypothesis. So, there is a significance relationship between Qualification Demographic factor and Awareness about the Fintech services.

5. Awareness Level Based on Income

In order to analysis the Awareness level of the Fintech Services by users based on their Income Socio Economic Characteristics the chi Square statistical tool has been adopted which helps in the finding the relationship between the Income and awareness level.

HYPOTHESIS

- **Ho:** There is no relationship between Income demographic factor and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.
- **H1:** There is a relationship between Income demographic factor and the Awareness about the Fintech Services.

Table 5: Evaluation of Awareness Level Based on Income

Income	Awareness about the Fintech Services	Not Awareness about the Fintech Services	Total
Less than Rs20000	36	10	46
Rs20000-Rs50000	44	03	47
Rs50000-Rs100000	01	00	01
Rs100000-Rs200000	00	00	00
More than Rs 200000	06	00	06
Total	87	13	100

The significance level=0.05, degree of Freedom: 4
 Calculated value is **5.971728** and the table value is **9.488**

Chart No 5: Awareness Level Based on Income

In the Chart No 5. The awareness level of fintech services by the users has been evaluated based on the Income Socio Economic Characteristics. Calculated value is less than table value so accepts the NULL Hypothesis and reject Alternative Hypothesis. So there is a no significance relationship between Income Demographic factor and Awareness about the Fintech service.

CHALLENGES FACED IN FINTECH ADOPTION

Security Issues

- **Fear of cyber-attacks and fraud:** The security of their financial information is a concern for many users. Security is a major worry for both tech-savvy and less tech-savvy people due to the increase in phishing, hacking, and identity theft instances.
- **Concerns about Data Privacy:** People may be reluctant to divulge financial and personal information online for fear of abuse or illegal access.
- **Insufficient Faith in Digital Platforms:** The idea that fintech platforms are less reliable than traditional banks is a barrier especially for elderly folks or people who are less tech-savvy.

2. Insufficient Knowledge of Digital Technology

- **Technological Proficiency:** Because of the intricacy of apps, interfaces and procedures using fintech services can be frightening for many people, particularly older persons or those with less education.
- **Limited Knowledge of Fintech Services:** Low adoption of fintech products (such as digital wallets and crypto currencies) may result from users' incomplete comprehension of its

features or advantages.

3. Problems with Infrastructure and Connectivity

- **Internet Access:** Despite Bengaluru's reputation as a digital hub, some parts of the city may still have trouble getting dependable internet. Users find it difficult to successfully use fintech services in areas with inadequate network infrastructure or in less connected neighborhoods.
- **Smartphone Access:** Although more people are using smartphones, some groups of people still do not have access to the devices, especially those with lower incomes.

4. Complexity and Usability

- **Complex User Interfaces:** A lot of fintech platforms may feature difficult-to-use interfaces that irritate users especially those who are not tech-savvy or are first-time users.
- **Regular upgrades:** Users, especially those who do not routinely interact with technology, may become confused by the frequent upgrades made to fintech apps and services.

FINDINGS

- Qualification and Age Factors impact more about on Fintech services.
- The age between 35-44 and 44-55 have fear about the Security and also about the trust issues due to lack of Financial Literacy about the Fintech Services.
- The age between 18-24 and 25-34 are more concern about the services Fees or Usability of Fintech Services.

CONCLUSION

The research on Enumerate the awareness and Challenges of Fintech services among different Demographic Factors in Bengaluru City offers important new insights into the ways in which the financial technology industry's rapid improvements are changing

how customers interact with financial services. Customer satisfaction has increased as a result of simplicity of use, especially among younger, tech-savvy consumers. With the advent of more recent technologies like block chain and crypto currencies, consumers are becoming more concerned about cyber security, data privacy and the possibility of fraud. In order to reduce the fear of the customer regarding the security the proper and stronger regulatory compliance to be made and transparent practice. The degree to which Fintech companies are able to resolve consumer problems and provide seamless user-friendly services will determine how long these technologies are adopted.

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